

Division by 0

Take the equation $\frac{1}{n} = 0$, here we can use $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty}$, to find out as n approaches infinity, the result will approach 0, thus when n is equal to infinity, the result shall be 0. Except, n is infinity, but the representation of infinity is different. After multiplying by n on both sides, we get $1 = 0n$, which breaks the rules of arithmetic, no number we know has this property, and after we divide by 0 on both sides, we get $n = \frac{1}{0}$ which is said to be infinity.

Let $\frac{1}{0}$ be a new number by itself, like $\sqrt{-1}$ or also known as i .

Let $\frac{1}{0}$ be \mathfrak{A}

From this, we can derive some axioms

List of Axioms

$\frac{1}{\mathfrak{A}} = 0$ as since \mathfrak{A} equals to $\frac{1}{0}$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\frac{1}{0}} \\ &= 1 \times \frac{0}{1} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved

$\frac{1}{0}$ is idempotent as long as the power is not 0 since, sticking to the basic definition of exponentiation as repeated multiplication, we can observe that $\frac{1}{0} \times \frac{1}{0} \times \frac{1}{0} \times \frac{1}{0} \times \dots$ will always result to $\frac{1}{0}$. Therefore, $\frac{1}{0}$ is idempotent

Any number added to $\frac{1}{0}$ will result in $\frac{1}{0}$ itself in which the other number is not in the form of $\frac{n}{0}$ where n is any number not equal to $\frac{1}{0}$. The proof of this is take a random number in the form of $\frac{x}{y}$.

Add it to $\frac{1}{0}$ or $\frac{1}{0}$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{x}{y} + \frac{1}{0} \\ &= \frac{x \times 0}{y \times 0} + \frac{1}{0} \\ &= \frac{0}{0} + \frac{1}{0} \\ &= \frac{1}{0} \end{aligned}$$

Hence proved

$\frac{n}{n}$ is equal to 0, where n is a random number not equal to $\frac{1}{0}$. The proof is $\frac{n}{n}$ can be simplified into $\frac{1}{1}$ which we know the answer as 0. Hence proved

$$\frac{0}{0} = 1 \text{ as since } \frac{1}{0} = 0$$

$$1 = 0 \cdot 0$$

$$1 = 0 \times \frac{1}{0}$$

$$1 = \frac{0}{0}$$

Hence proved

$\sqrt[n]{0} = 0$ where n is not equal to 0, as

$$\sqrt[n]{0}$$

$$= 0^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

And since 0 is idempotent

$$= 0$$

Hence proved

$\sqrt[0]{0} = 1$ as

$$\sqrt[0]{0}$$

$$= 0^{\frac{1}{0}}$$

$\frac{1}{0} = 0$, therefore

$$= 0^0$$

$$= 1$$

Hence proved

$0 \cdot 0 = 0$ As

$$\begin{aligned}
& 0_{\mathfrak{A}} \\
&= 0 \times \frac{1}{0} \\
&= \frac{0}{0} \\
&= 1
\end{aligned}$$

Hence proved

When doing distribution with \mathfrak{A} , everything inside the bracket must first be simplified into its simplest form before continuing as

$$(n)_{\mathfrak{A}}$$

Where n is a random number not equal to \mathfrak{A}

$$\begin{aligned}
&= (n + 0)_{\mathfrak{A}} \\
&= n_{\mathfrak{A}} + 0_{\mathfrak{A}} \\
&= n_{\mathfrak{A}} + 1
\end{aligned}$$

Which is different from the original result which is $n_{\mathfrak{A}}$

Distribution by \mathfrak{A} is supposed to be done for complex numbers only

Graphical Representation

To add the \mathfrak{A} , we must add on to the complex plane, extending into 3 dimensions. In this plane, there will be 2 origins, one for imaginary and real numbers, which is 0 since $0i = 0$, and one for \mathfrak{A}

and real numbers, which will be 1 since $0_{\text{अ}} = 1$

To describe points in the complex plane (real and imaginary), we add the real part of the point and the imaginary part. If we do the same for this extended plane, we need to add the अ part, real part, and imaginary part. Since, anything added to अ will equal अ itself. On the plane of अ or $2_{\text{अ}}$ or $3_{\text{अ}}$ and so on, every point on that plane will equal to अ, $2_{\text{अ}}$, $3_{\text{अ}}$, and so on.

This representation is similar to that of the spacetime of our universe. It is said that right now, the big bang did not happen from a singular point on spacetime, it happened on every point, as when the big bang happened, spacetime itself was created. Therefore, theoretically every single point of spacetime is the same, similar to that of the extended plane with अ

~by Vedant Wagle

